

Aromatic nuclear acetamidation by the anodic oxidation at the platinum electrode

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Abstract : Aromatic nuclear acetamidation of some aromatic compounds naphthalene, *p*-xylene, 3,4-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid and methyl *p*-hydroxybenzoate have been carried out at platinum electrode under the process of nuclear oxidation. The removal of electrons from the aromatic π -electron system were achieved by the electrochemical oxidation. The electrolysis were carried out at the constant anode potential in an electrolytic cell assembly containing reaction mixture and electrodes. The products formed during the electrolysis are reported here.

Keywords : Nuclear acetamidation, nuclear oxidation, electrolysis, platinum electrode, green chemistry.

Introduction

In the present communication we are reporting the result of our studies on the nuclear acetamidation of aromatic compounds viz. naphthalene, *p*-xylene, 3,4-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid and methyl *p*-hydroxybenzoate. The reaction is an important example of nuclear oxidation which is not easily possible by the conventional chemical synthetic methods. The nuclear acetamidation is a substitution of acetamido group on benzene nucleus through oxidative nuclear substitution. The electrolysis in all these reactions were carried out at constant potential by using a conventional three electrode cell assembly with working as well as counter electrodes of platinum and saturated calomel electrode as reference electrode.

Results and discussion

The nuclear acetamidation of aromatic compounds does not require any reagent, catalyst or acid and base. It takes place through the free radicals in the solution. Good reviews are available for the free radical reactions¹⁻⁴. Electrode processes in the realm of organic reactions are accredited⁵ over conventional organic processes with some specialities such as anode and cathode, whose potentials can be controlled at will, acts as oxidant and reductant

for a substrate. Singh⁶ and Kumar⁷ have studied various anodic processes at the platinum electrode.

Electrochemical reactions have attracted much attention due to several advantages such as rapid reaction rates and higher yield of pure products with non-polluting nature of the reactant^{5,8}. The removal of electrons from aromatic π -electron systems may be achieved by electrochemical oxidation and the resulting aromatic cation radical or other aromatic cationic species undergoes a variety of reactions⁸ such as aromatic substitution⁹⁻¹² and coupling.

Aromatic nuclear acetamidation have been achieved by the anodic oxidation of aromatic compounds in the presence of acetonitrile^{13,14}.

The important aspect of this electrochemical study is to identify that which component of this reaction solution is actually undergoing electron transfer. In fact, all nuclear substitutions, were thought to involve attack on the hydrocarbon by an electrochemically generated reagent. The voltammetric data shows that the primary electrochemical step in the nuclear substitution is the oxidation of the hydrocarbon^{13,14}, since the benzene ring is easily oxidisable in comparison to this substituting group. Although it is not necessary that all anodic reactions are initiated by oxidation of the aromatic substrate.

The proposed pathway for the nuclear acetamidation has been formulated in the following way (Scheme 1).

The factors governing which of the two alternatives whether the nuclear substitution or addition is actually

Scheme 1

Now it is generally accepted that in most of the oxidations of aromatic hydrocarbons removal of one electron from the hydrocarbon affords a radical cation. Both the structure of the radical cation and the environment in which it is created play crucial role to dictate its subsequent reactions. It would be expected for the nuclear aromatic substitution and addition to be most favoured in the presence of strong nucleophiles and when the ring is not highly alkylated. This is due to the less stable benzylic type carbocation stabilized by hyperconjugation i.e. the alkyl substituents enhance the stability of benzylic carbocation or radical formed in the initial stage. In such cases the attacking centre becomes alkylated group. In this nuclear oxidation, acetonitrile works as a strong nucleophile which precedes the reaction.

Now the nucleophile is another reactant which can attack the ring to afford a cationic intermediate which most commonly loses a proton after the second electron transfer to regenerate the aromatic ring and afford a nuclear substitution product. In special cases it may suffer attack by a second molecule of nucleophile to afford an addition product (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

chosen are not fully clear but it appears that path of the nuclear substitution is always preferred. It seems reasonable since loss of the proton restores the aromatic stability and therefore has a low activation energy, which is observed only in the simple benzenoid hydrocarbon systems¹⁵.

In this system the reaction takes place at the room temperature in a potential range 1.80 V to 2.80 V but the specific potential for the reaction from various observations is found to be approximately 2.5 V vs Hg/Hg^{2+} . During electrolysis 0.5–3.0 F mol^{-1} of electricity was passed which is very small in comparison to energy used in other conventional methods.

All the electrolysis were carried out at their corresponding oxidation potentials and were completed in 3 h. After three hour no oxidation product was seen to diffuse in the bulk. All the products were solid, coloured and entirely different from the starting compound. The observations recorded in these reactions are depicted in Table 1.

Among the product 3a and 3b, 3a is a major product due to greater steric hindrance at position 3 for the substitution of acetamido group. Whereas in 4a and 4b, 4a is a major product which is stabilized due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding (Table 2). The products 3a and 4a were separated and purified by preparative chromatographic technique ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{14} : \text{C}_6\text{H}_6$, 4 : 6, v/v).

Table 1. Current-potential data of electrolysis as recorded by potentiostat

Time	Current in mA			
	Naphthalene	<i>p</i> -Xylene	3,4-Dimethoxyphenylacetic acid	Methyl <i>p</i> -hydroxybenzoate
3 h	15.50	34.40	50.00	38.60
	15.35	34.20	48.60	38.00
	15.28	34.05	47.10	36.60
	15.15	33.80	45.50	34.50
	15.05	33.65	44.56	33.80
	15.00	33.55	43.80	32.60
	14.80	33.40	41.80	31.40
	14.65	33.20	40.20	30.00
	14.50	33.10	39.00	28.60
	14.30	32.80	38.30	27.50
	14.10	32.65	37.15	25.90
	14.00	32.50	36.20	25.50
	13.70	32.25	35.50	25.10
Applied potential (V)	2.50	2.50	2.21	2.63

Table 2. Reactants, products, reaction time and the ratio of the yield

Sl. no.	Reactant	Product	Yield (%)	Time (h)
1.	Naphthalene	<i>N</i> -Acetyl naphthylamine (1)	96	3
2.	<i>p</i> -Xylene	2,5-Dimethyl acetanilide (2)	97	3
3.	3,4-Dimethoxy phenylacetic acid	3-(<i>N</i> -Acetyl)amino-4,5-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid (3a)	70	
		2-(<i>N</i> -Acetyl)amino-4,5-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid (3b)	30	3
4.	Methyl <i>p</i> -hydroxybenzoate	Methyl 3-(<i>N</i> -acetyl)amino-4-hydroxybenzoate (4a)	65	
		Methyl 2-(<i>N</i> -acetyl)amino-4-hydroxybenzoate (4b)	35	3

Conclusion :

It is obvious from the studies that the electrochemical nuclear acetamidation as a nuclear substitution in aromatic compounds provides a good method for the aromatic nuclear oxidation which is not so easy by chemical method. The method does not require any special condition to maintain the reaction temperature since the electrolysis was carried out at room temperature. Therefore the method is simple, ecofriendly and a part of green chemistry. The unique feature of this reaction is that acetonitrile works as a solvent as well as nucleophile for the substitution.

Experimental

Reaction mixture : The reaction mixture contains the

25 mL of 0.1 mol solution of starting material using acetonitrile (CH₃CN) as a solvent and 25 mL of the 0.1 mol aqueous solution of KCl, which is used as supporting electrolyte¹⁶. In this reaction acetonitrile works as a solvent as well as nucleophile for the substitution.

Reagents : All the compounds naphthalene, *p*-xylene, 3,4-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid and methyl *p*-hydroxybenzoate, acetonitrile, mercury, KCl and chloroform were of AnalaR grade. Water used was double distilled.

Electrolysis : The controlled potential electrolysis were performed at room temperature in conventional three electrode cell assembly containing platinum¹⁷ (flattened sheet

of dimension 1.0 cm × 1.0 cm) as working as well as counter electrode and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode. Magnetic stirrer was used for the proper mixing of reaction mixture. The current potential data was recorded with the help of potentiostat.

The products were extracted from the reaction mixture to chloroform by simple solvent extraction method after diluting the reaction solution with double distilled water. Two immiscible layers of above solvent were shaken in separatory funnel and allowed to settle, after some time the chloroform layer containing desired product was removed and dried. The products were obtained after evaporation of chloroform and subsequent recrystallization.

Spectral analysis of the products :

The melting points of all synthesized compounds were recorded on a VEB Wagetchink Rapio PHMK05 instrument and were uncorrected. ¹H NMR (300, 300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75, 300 MHz) spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX 300 FT spectrometer in CDCl₃ using tetramethylsilane (TMS) (δ 0.0 ppm, ¹H NMR spectra) or C₆D₆ (δ 127.8 ppm, ¹³C NMR spectra) as internal reference. Chemical shifts are on parts per million (ppm) relative to TMS. Microanalyses were carried out in the Elementar Vario EL III instrument. IR spectra in KBr were recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR 8201 PC IR spectrophotometer (4000–400 cm⁻¹).

N-Acetyl naphthylamine (1) : Yield 96%; mol. wt. 185; m.p. 160 °C; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 735, 860, 910 (substituted benzene), 1608 (C=C aromatic), 1681 (C=O), 2830 (C-H), 3035 (=C-H aromatic), 3428 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 2.72 (3H, s, COCH₃), 7.25–7.69 (7H, m, Ar-H), 8.15 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 50.8 (NHCOCH₃), 122.1, 122.1, 122.1, 122.1, 122.1, 125.7, 128.5, 129.5, 135.1 (10 aromatic C), 163.0 (NHCOCH₃) (Found : C, 77.43; H, 5.62; N, 7.36. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₁NO : C, 77.83; H, 5.94; N, 7.56%).

2,5-Dimethyl acetanilide (2) : Yield 97%; mol. wt. 163; m.p. 139 °C; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 735, 870, 915 (substituted benzene), 1610 (C=C aromatic), 1685 (C=O), 2930 (CH₃), 3030 (=C-H aromatic), 3420 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 2.39 (6H, s, CH₃), 2.71 (3H, s, COCH₃), 7.61 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 8.78

(1H, s, Ar-H), 8.13 (1H, s, NH); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 14.4 (2CH₃), 51.3 (NHCOCH₃), 125.4, 125.4, 125.4, 128.5, 129.1, 138.4 (6 aromatic C), 163.5 (NHCOCH₃) (Found : C, 73.02; H, 7.65; N, 8.32. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₃NO : C, 73.61; H, 7.97; N, 8.58%).

3-(N-Acetyl)amino-4,5-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid (3a) : Yield 70%; mol. wt. 253; m.p. 67 °C; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 745, 860, 935 (substituted benzene), 1655, 1695 (C=O), 1705 (COOH), 2815 (O-CH₃), 2940 (aliphatic C-H), 3030 (=C-H aromatic), 3425 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 2.35 (6H, s, OCH₃), 2.72 (3H, s, COCH₃), 5.3 (2H, s, CH₂), 8.16 (1H, s, NH), 8.65 (1H, s, Ar-H), 8.76 (1H, s, Ar-H), 12 (1H, s, COOH); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 46.2 and 50.4 (OCH₃), 51.1 (NHCOCH₃), 88.0 (CH₂COOH) 126.8, 134.5, 136.1, 138.2, 138.3, 151.0 (6 aromatic C), 163.2 (NHCOCH₃), 172.6 (COOH) (Found : C, 56.11; H, 5.62; N, 5.21. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₅NO₅ : C, 56.91; H, 5.92; N, 5.53%).

2-(N-Acetyl)amino-4,5-dimethoxyphenylacetic acid (3b) : Yield 30%; mol. wt. 253; m.p. 69 °C; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 736, 845, 933 (substituted benzene), 1655, 1695 (C=O), 2944 (aliphatic C-H), 3036 (=C-H aromatic), 3325 (NH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 2.35 (6H, s, OCH₃), 2.70 (3H, s, COCH₃), 5.2 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.75 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 8.17 (1H, s, NH), 12.0 (1H, s, COOH); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 46.7 and 50.2 (OCH₃), 51.2 (NHCOCH₃), 88.3 (CH₂COOH), 125.3, 126.1, 126.2, 138.2, 138.5, 139.1 (6 aromatic C), 163.4 (NHCOCH₃), 172.2 (COOH) (Found : C, 56.19; H, 5.52; N, 5.30. Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₅NO₅ : C, 56.91; H, 5.92; N, 5.53%).

Methyl 3-(N-acetyl)amino-4-hydroxybenzoate (4a) : Yield 65%; mol. wt. 209; m.p. 108 °C; IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹) : 750, 865, 955 (substituted benzene), 1060 (ester C-O), 1608 (C=C aromatic), 1710 (COO-), 1725 (C=O), 2940 (aliphatic C-H), 3033 (=C-H aromatic), 3430 (NH), 3590 (OH); ¹H NMR (300 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 2.0 (1H, s, OH, exchangeable with D₂O), 2.70 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.82 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 6.76 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 8.15 (1H, s, NH), 8.75 (1H, s, Ar-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz; CDCl₃/TMS) : δ 50 (COOCH₃), 51.8 (NHCOCH₃), 126.1, 129.0, 129.8, 134.6, 135.4, 138.3 (6 aromatic C), 161.2 (COOCH₃), 163.2 (NHCOCH₃) (Found : C,

56.91; H, 5.02; N, 6.25. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{11}NO_4$: C, 57.41; H, 5.26; N, 6.69%.

Methyl 2-(N-acetyl)amino-4-hydroxybenzoate (4b) : Yield 35%; mol. wt. 209; m.p. 111 °C; IR ν_{max} (cm^{-1}) : 735, 793, 865 (substituted benzene), 1060 (ester C-O), 1608 (C=C aromatic), 1710 (COO-), 1725 (C=O), 2940 (aliphatic C-H), 3420 (NH), 3590 (OH); 1H NMR (300 MHz; $CDCl_3/TMS$) : δ 2.0 (1H, s, OH, exchangeable with D_2O), 2.72 (3H, s, $COCH_3$), 3.83 (3H, s, $COOCH_3$), 6.94 (2H, d, J 8.6 Hz, Ar-H), 8.15 (1H, s, NH), 8.77 (1H, s, Ar-H); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz; $CDCl_3/TMS$) : δ 51.5 ($NHCOCH_3$), 52.6 ($COOCH_3$), 125.4, 125.6, 129.1, 129.3, 138.0, 138.4 (6 aromatic C), 161.2 ($COOCH_3$), 163.1 ($NHCOCH_3$) (Found : C, 56.89; H, 5.08; N, 6.19. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{11}NO_4$: C, 57.41; H, 5.26; N, 6.69%).

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